

European AI Security network CrossTalk event: leading the future of AI in Healthcare

10 EU funded projects will discuss with European authorities
their solutions on AI and Cybersecurity

Brussels, October 22, 2024 – On October 22nd, the **European AI Security Network (EASiNet)** will host a highly anticipated **CrossTalk Event** at the **Delegation of the Emilia-Romagna Region to the EU** in Brussels. This exclusive, invitation-only event is set to be a milestone in the collaboration between European-funded AI and cybersecurity projects and key European authorities.

The event will showcase innovative solutions developed by ten major **EU-funded projects**, which include **TRUMPET, FLUTE, ENCRYPT, HARPOCRATES, PAROMA-MED, KATY, ONCOVALUE, AI4EOSC, EOSC-TITAN, EOSC-SIESTA**

These projects form a network of more than **50 partners** across Europe as hospitals, ICT companies, legal agencies, research institutes, collaborating to address crucial challenges in **Cloud Security, Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs)**, and **Federated Learning** for healthcare applications. Each of these projects is at the forefront of research aimed at creating secure, privacy-preserving frameworks that will play a vital role in the future of healthcare and AI technologies.

The event will also feature distinguished contributions from **ENISA**, and from the **European Commission** - DG SANTE, DG CONNECT - whose representatives will provide critical insights into ongoing and future European policies. The discussions will focus on how these policies can support the implementation of AI-driven innovations while ensuring strong data protection and privacy standards.

Key topics addressed during the event:

- **Cloud Security for Data:** Innovations in secure data storage and processing in cloud environments.
- **Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs):** Cutting-edge methods, including encryption and data watermarking, to protect sensitive data.
- **Federated Learning Adoption and Certification in Healthcare:** The challenges and opportunities of implementing Federated Learning in healthcare, including regulatory compliance and privacy-preserving data-sharing platforms.

Francesco Ghini, Dissemination and Communication Manager of **Istituto Romagnolo per la Cura dei Tumori “Dino Amadori” IRST srl** for the TRUMPET and FLUTE projects, highlighted the importance of creating collaborative platforms like this event: *“We created this event with the aim of taking concrete steps in the field of AI and cybersecurity by bringing together leading scientists across Europe who are working on future solutions.*

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Connecting them with authorities is pivotal for building the foundations of Europe's future AI landscape.” Ghini added: “Today, it is quite difficult to create convergent efforts between EU-funded projects and the authorities operating in the same field. Events like this aim to close that gap, optimize efforts, and align all actors to a common objective: shaping the future of AI in Europe.”

Info & contact

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